

Polymer Composites

ICCM 2023

Bearing Strength High Performance Fibre Metal Thin-Ply Laminates

H. Wittich, B. Kötter, K. Yamada,
J. Körbelin, K. Kawabe, M. Nishikawa,
M. Hojo, B. Fiedler

Institute of Polymer and Composites
Hamburg University of Technology

Belfast, 2023

Thin-Ply composites

- Carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP)
- Layer thickness below 60 μm , typically 30 μm
- Tow spreading process

Increased lightweight potential

- More degrees of freedom in design
 - Low influence of design-rules
 - Possibilities to optimize the laminate
 - Thinner laminates
- Higher laminate qualities

30 g/m²

360 g/m²

Damage mechanisms Thin-Ply

- In-situ strength: Higher strength with decreasing layer thickness
- Damage initiation shifts to higher stresses
- Suppression of delaminations

Damage mechanisms Thin-Ply

- Significantly reduced damage formation at stress concentration
- Significantly reduced strength with decreasing layer thickness (tension)
 - Stress concentrations are the limiting factor when using Thin-Ply composites

Thin-Ply Fibre Metal laminates (FML)

Concept: Hybridisation through metal

- Increased energy dissipation
 - Plastic deformation
 - Work hardening
- Distribution of stresses
 - Higher local stiffness

Potential of Thin-Ply FML

- Lower interlaminar shear stresses
 - Surface pre-treatment less critical
- Increased degrees of freedom in design
 - Weight proportion and position of metal layers
 - Complex geometries possible

Design of Experiments – Thin-Ply FML

Materials:

- TR50S Carbon fibers, Mitsubishi, Japan
- Bisphenol-A epoxy resin, ITCF (jER828:jER1001)
- Stainless steel foil 1.4310

Manufacturing:

Curing at 125°C and 4 bar pressure at the autoclave

Fiber weight per area

40 g/m² ≈ 40 μm

160 g/m² ≈ 160 μm

Thickness of the metal foil

40 μm

160 μm

Hybridization

25 Vol.-% Stainless Steel

12.5 Vol.-% Stainless Steel

6.25 Vol.-% Stainless Steel

Layup

[45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m]_{ns}

Interlaminar properties:

Experiments:

ILSS

DCB – Mode I

ENF – Mode II

Pre-treatment

Sol-Gel Process

Etching

Abrasive

Plasma

Open Hole Tension:

Near field strain:
Optical measurement

Bore diameter:
6 mm

Bearing:

Displacement:
Optical measurement

Bolt diameter:
6 mm

Surface Pre-Treatment

Surface Pre-Treatment:

- Reference: Cleaned with alcohol
- Acids
 - Sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4)
 - Hydrofluoric acid (HF)
 - Hydrochloric acid (HCl)
- Cold Plasma-treatment
- Abrasive
 - #500 abrasive paper
 - #500 + cold plasma
 - #500 + Sol-Gel (AC-130-2)

Open Hole Tension – Thin-Ply FML

- Decreasing strength with decreasing layer thickness
- Increasing strength with increasing metal content
- Hybrid Thick-Ply specimens fail due to delaminations

Bearing

Bearing

- Maximum achievable stress increases with increasing metal content
- Progressive failure behaviour of the hybrid Thin-Ply specimens

Bearing

- Maximum achievable stress increases with increasing metal content
- Progressive failure behaviour of the hybrid Thin-Ply specimens

Bearing – Micrographs

Thick-Ply Reference

Thin-Ply 6,25 % SF

Thin-Ply 12.5 % SF

Thin-Ply 25.0 % SF

- Progressive failure behaviour due to local damage
- Metal foils increase bending stiffness → Resistance against buckling

Bearing – Thin-Ply FML

- Increasing bearing strength with increasing metal content
- Thin-Ply with a steel content of 6,25 % has the best specific performance

The drawback: Stress concentrations are the limiting factor when using Thin-Ply composites

Can be compensated and even improved by metal layers in the area of the bolt

Kötter, Benedikt and Yamada, Kohei and Körbelin, Johann and Kawabe, Kazumasa and Nishikawa, Masaaki and Hojo, Masaki and Fiedler, Bodo (2021).

Steel foil reinforcement for high performance bearing strength in Thin Ply composites.

Composites Part C: Open Access. 4. 100085

Thank you for your attention

Polymer Composites

Industrial Technology
Center of Fukui Prefecture

Dr. Hans Wittich
Institute of polymer and composites
Hamburg University of Technology
wittich@tuhh.de

Institut für Kunststoffe und Verbundwerkstoffe, Les Menuires, 2023

Open Hole Tension – Thin-Ply FML

Thin-Ply Ref.

Thin-Ply 25 % SF

Thin-Ply 12.5 % SF

- Larger fracture surfaces with increasing metal content
- Plastic deformation of the metal

Open Hole Tension – Thin-Ply FML

Thin-Ply:

- Less interlaminar shear stresses
- Continuous stress gradient in the transition zone

} Suppression of delamination